

Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium(V) as Mixed Ligand Complexes of Various Hydroxyamidines and Thiocyanate**

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Manuscript received 31 December 1981, revised 24 May 1982, accepted 21 August 1982

A simple and selective method for the extractive spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V) in various alloy steels at micro-gram level has been developed. The method is based on the chloroform extraction of vanadium(V) with eleven newly synthesized hydroxyamidines (HOA) and thiocyanate. The molar absorbances of the complexes lie between $3.30 - 6.25 \times 10^4 \text{ l. mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 595-610 nm with Sandell's sensitivities in the range 0.008-0.015 μg of metal per cm^2 . In present investigation N-hydroxy-N-p-chlorophenyl-N'-(2,3-dimethyl)phenylbenzamidinium hydrochloride was selected for a detailed study. It forms a deep-green complex in the pH range 1.7-3.0 having the ratio 1 : 2 : 2 (V : SCN^- : HOA). Fe(III), Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Mn(II), Cr(III), Ti(IV), Zr(IV), Nb(V), Mo(VI), W(VI), fluoride, iodide, thio-sulphate, oxalate, phosphate etc. do not interfere.

N-Hydroxy-N,N'-diarylbenzamidinium (HOA) and its derivatives have been recently explored as potential reagents for the determination of various d-group elements¹⁻⁵. HOA is a better reagent than other well known organic reagents⁶⁻⁸, because of its high molecular weight and selective colour reaction towards the metal ions. However, there is considerable scope for improvement in the structural features of such a molecule to make it more suitable as an analytical reagent, as substitution is possible in three phenyl rings. The objective of the present communication is to study the colour reaction of eleven newly synthesized N-hydroxy-N,N'-diarylbenzamidines (I), with vanadium(V) in presence of thiocyanate with a view to study the effect of substituents on the complexing properties of the $-\text{N}=\text{C}-\text{N}(\text{OH})-$ group.

X = H-
Y = H-, o-CH₃-, m-CH₃-, p-CH₃-, 2,3-(CH₃)₂-,
2,5-(CH₃)₂-, 2,6-(CH₃)₂- or p-OCH₃-
Z = H-, m-Cl-, p-Cl- or p-CH₃-

N-Hydroxy-N-p-chlorophenyl-N'-(2,3-dimethyl)-phenylbenzamidinium hydrochloride was found to be the most sensitive reagent in the present investigation and hence selected for the detailed study.

The advantages of the proposed method over the recommended methods⁹⁻¹³ are that the colour reaction is simple, rapid, sensitive and fairly selective. The ions Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Ti^{4+} , Zr^{4+} , Mo^{6+} and oxidizing agents do not interfere and there is no possibility of reduction of vanadium(V).

Experimental

Absorptiometric and pH-metric measurements were made with an ECIL, UV-VIS spectrophotometer, model GS-865 with matched 1 cm quartz and silica cells and Systronic pH-meter, type-322, respectively.

Vanadium(V) solution was prepared from ammonium metavanadate (B.D.H., AnalaR) and standardized volumetrically using potassium permanganate¹⁴. The reagent was prepared by the condensation of equimolar quantities of N-arylbenzimidoylchloride and N-arylhydroxylamine in ether medium¹.

A 0.1% (w/v) solution of hydroxyamidine in chloroform and 5% (w/v) solution of potassium thiocyanate in water were used for the extraction work.

Procedure: An aliquot of the vanadium(V) solution (100 μg V) and 2 ml of thiocyanate solution were taken in a 125 ml separatory funnel and the pH was maintained at 2.2 in final dilution of 15 ml using HCl-KCl buffer. The aqueous layer was equilibrated with 15 ml chloroform solution of the reagent for 1 min. The organic layer was transferred over anhydrous sodium sulphate in a

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** Presented at Annual Convention of Chemists, 1980, held at Bombay.

50 ml beaker. The aqueous phase was washed with 2 × 4 ml portions of chloroform. The combined extracts, after drying, were transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask and the volume was made up to the mark with chloroform. The absorbances were measured at 605 nm against chloroform as a blank.

Results and Discussion

The absorption curve of reagent and its metal chelate showed that the reagent has negligible absorption in the region 450-700 nm, while the complex has a broad λ_{max} between 595-610 nm.

Effect of variables : Chloroform was chosen as a diluent for this study because of higher extractability of the complex and the reagent in it than other solvents (benzene, carbon tetrachloride and 2,4-dichlorobenzene). The pH of the aqueous phase was maintained with 1 M hydrochloric acid and dilute ammonia. The optimum pH range for complete extraction of metal was found to be 1.7-3.0. At least 8 and 10 fold molar excess of hydroxyamidine and thiocyanate respectively were necessary for complete extraction of the metal. Addition of more reagent caused no adverse effect either in the position of λ_{max} or on the absorbance value of the complex. The order of addition of reagents was not critical. A time of 1 min was sufficient for complete extraction of vanadium(V). The complex was stable for atleast 40 hr at room temperature. Variation in temperature from 20 to 40° and volume of the aqueous phase from 15 to 60 ml had no effect on the nature of the complex. No effect of electrolytes (i.e. NaCl, KCl and NH₄Cl) upto 3 M on the distribution coefficient of the metal was observed.

Effect of substituents : The influence of substituents on the complexing properties of the ligand was studied by preparing eleven new analogues of N-hydroxy-N,N'-diarylbenzamidines and testing their potentialities in the extractive separation and spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V). The molar absorptivities of the mixed ligand complexes were calculated on the basis of vanadium content at respective λ_{max} as shown in Table 1. It is observed that the position of λ_{max} is not appreciably affected by the substitution of N-phenyl or N'-phenyl ring. However, the absorptivity of the complex is affected markedly by the substitution of both phenyl rings. An alkyl group, introduced in the N'-phenyl ring, greatly affected the absorptivity of the complex. The substitution of this phenyl ring resulted into hyperchromic shift, the order being 2,5-(CH₃)₂ > 2,3-(CH₃)₂ > o-CH₃ > p-CH₃ > m-CH₃ (Comp. 1-4, 6 and 8), and hypochromic shift in the order 2,6-(CH₃)₂ > p-(OCH₃) (Comp. 1, 5 and 7). The substitution of N-phenyl ring also showed hyperchromic shift in the order p-Cl > m-Cl > p-CH

TABLE 1—SPECTRAL DATA OF VANADIUM(V)-THIOCYANATE COMPLEXES WITH HYDROXYAMIDINES IN CHLOROFORM

Sl. No.	X	Y	λ_{max} nm	ϵ 1.mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	Sandell's sensitivity $\mu\text{g V cm}^{-2}$
1.	H -	m-Cl -	595	4800	0.01061
2.	o-CH ₃ -	m-Cl -	600	5400	0.00945
3.	m-CH ₃ -	m-Cl -	600	4800	0.01061
4.	p-CH ₃ -	m-Cl -	595	4800	0.01061
5.	p-OCH ₃ -	m-Cl -	595	4700	0.01083
6.	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂ -	m-Cl -	600	6100	0.00835
7.	2,6-(CH ₃) ₂ -	m-Cl -	600	3300	0.01543
8.	2,3-(CH ₃) ₂ -	m-Cl -	600	6000	0.00849
9.	2,3-(CH ₃) ₂ -	H -	600	5250	0.00970
10.	2,3-(CH ₃) ₂ -	p-CH ₃ -	610	5650	0.00901
11.	2,3-(CH ₃) ₂ -	p-Cl -	605	6250	0.00815

No. 1, 4 and 5 are free bases.

As expected from the above observation, N-hydroxy-N-p-chlorophenyl-N'-(2,3-dimethyl)phenylbenzamidine hydrochloride is found to be the most sensitive reagent in the present investigation.

Concentration ranges, molar absorbance, sensitivity and precision of the method : The effective molar absorptivities of the coloured complexes lie in the range of 3.30 - 6.25 × 10³ 1.mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and the sensitivities¹⁵ of the reaction lie between 0.008-0.015 $\mu\text{g V cm}^{-2}$ as shown in Table 1. The method obeys Beer's law upto 7.2 ppm of vanadium. The optimum concentration range on the basis of Ringbom plot¹⁶ lie between 1.2-6.8 ppm of the metal. The mean absorbance value and relative standard deviation of the method are found to be 0.490 and $\pm 0.67\%$, respectively (results of 10 measurements, each containing 100 $\mu\text{g V}/25$ ml).

Composition of the complex : The ratio of vanadium(V) to hydroxyamidine or thiocyanate was studied by mole ratio¹⁷, slope ratio¹⁸ and Job's method of continuous variation¹⁹. The results obtained indicated that the complex consists of 2 molecules each of hydroxyamidine and thiocyanate for each molecule of vanadium. The probable composition of the neutral mixed complex is VO.2SCN.OA.HOA.

Effect of diverse ions : The effect of various ions in the separation and subsequent spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V) was studied, following the recommended procedure. Chloride, bromide, nitrate, sulphate, borate, phosphate, triethanolamine, alkali and alkaline-earth elements did not interfere upto 2000 ppm. Fe(III) interfered due to coextraction of its ternary complex but its interference could be eliminated by masking it with trisodium phosphate. Mo(VI) is also coextracted

as a binary yellowish complex but did not interfere at the absorption maxima. The interference of Cu(II) was eliminated by masking it with thiourea. The tolerated amount* of other ions (in ppm), in the determination of 4 ppm of vanadium(V) are shown in parenthesis: Cd²⁺, Zn²⁺ (1000); Cu²⁺ (1200); Ni²⁺ (500); Co²⁺ (400); Mn²⁺ (600); Cr³⁺ and Al³⁺ (500 ppm); Cs⁺, Rb⁺, La³⁺ (1000); Fe³⁺, Bi³⁺, Th⁴⁺ (800); Zr⁴⁺ (80), Ti⁴⁺ (80); Nb⁵⁺ (60); Mo⁶⁺ (80); W⁶⁺ (40); U⁶⁺ (400); F⁻ (400); I⁻ (500); IO₃⁻ (100); arsenate (400).

Application of the method: The method has been applied successfully to three BCS steels, two V-W steels (64a and 241/1) and one tungsten free steel (252). The results of the determinations are summarized in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM IN VARIOUS BCS STEELS

Sample	Vanadium found ^a %	Certified %	Standard deviation
64a Alloy steel	1.553	1.57	± 0.0059
241/1 High speed steel	1.551	1.57	+ 0.0051
252 Low alloy steel	0.450	0.46	± 0.0064

^a = An average of six determinations.

BCS = British Chemical Standards, Bureau of Analysed Samples Ltd., Newham Hall, Middlebrough, Yorks.

The sample containing about 2 mg of vanadium was dissolved in dilute nitric acid and oxides of nitrogen were removed by boiling. The insoluble matters were removed by filtration. The filtrate was made up to 250 ml in a volumetric flask and vanadium content of the sample was determined as mentioned in the recommended procedure.

* Error less than 2%.

Acknowledgement

Thanks of the authors are due to Prof. S. G. Tandon, Head, Dept. of Chemistry, Ravishankar University, Raipur for facilities and to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for awarding a Senior Research Fellowship to one of them (A.R.J.).

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